

RELATIONSHIPS OF PHYSICS AND ART

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Anatasia

In the Aristotelian system, knowledge is divided into three types: productive knowledge, which is a means of producing results for the benefit of mankind, practical knowledge, which guides behavior, and theoretical knowledge, which cannot be used as a tool for any purpose. This type of information is usually seen as unrelated and independent information fields. This article argues that this notion is not correct and tries to explain the relationship between the mentioned fields of knowledge by revealing the relationship between theoretical knowledge and productive knowledge. For this, first of all, the subject of physical science should be determined, and then the connection of natural art (non-practical art) with physics should be determined. By explaining this law, the concepts of "productive knowledge", "productive art" and "theoretical knowledge" and the relationship between these concepts are intended to be made clear and clear. Clarification of these concepts and the relationship between them also shows the debt of the modern classification of sciences to Aristotle; It provides a theoretical framework for understanding the relationship between modern engineering sciences and the basic sciences (physics, chemistry, and biology).

Key words: Aristotle, art, technique, theoretical science, physics

INTRODUCTION

Aristotle begins Book I of Metaphysics with the fact that man has a natural desire to know. Although there is no reason in this phrase, there is a sign: the use of senses, which are the source of knowledge, gives people pleasure. Aristotle then begins to explain the levels of knowledge in a hierarchical manner: at the bottom is intuitive perception (aisthêton), above it is the recall of repeated perceptions (mnêmê), experience resulting from accumulation in memory (empeiria), art formed by knowledge (tekhnê) added to experience, and at the bottom is metaphysics, pure knowledge of first principles and causes. But metaphysics is not only concerned with first principles and causes; It is also a science that examines existence not in terms of being mobile or alive, but in terms of being itself. However, not intelligent mortal or immortal beings (heavenly spheres) are inaudible, but only thinkable (noeta) and eternally real beings (pure forms), which cannot exist, that is, God, the general shape (generic

shape is not possible). cut off from existence).) examines the heavenly minds and the intuitive mind (nous) in man.

Aristotle's *Metaphysics*, Chapter VI. In his book, he distinguishes these research topics from other theoretical disciplines of physics and mathematics. Accordingly, physics is the theoretical science that studies primary substances that are subject to formation and decay, have independent existence and forms inseparable from matter; Mathematics is a theoretical science that studies bodies that are motionless, but cannot exist independently of matter (numbers and spatial forms that describe primary substances); *Metaphysics* is the theoretical science that deals with entities independent of matter and inert. Theoretical sciences differ from arts (tekhnê), which use knowledge to produce profit, and applied sciences, which use it to direct action; they don't use knowledge for the sake of using it. it is a means to any end. They seek knowledge for its own sake. Moreover, applied and productive sciences deal with the contingent, and theoretical sciences deal with the necessary, in other words, with things that cannot be otherwise. Hence, the knowledge produced by the theoretical sciences must be exact knowledge, or at least aspire to exact knowledge.

The art of mathematics

The art of medicine is not a mathematical art and consists of a theoretical component provided directly by the physical sciences and a practical component provided by experience. In other words, the science on which the art of medicine depends is physics. But the Aristotelian line characterizes some arts as mathematical; Because these arts are between physics, which deals with real things, and mathematics, which deals with abstract things, such as optics, mechanics, astronomy, and music. Physical objects have surfaces, volumes, lines, and points that mathematics deals with, but mathematics does not examine these qualities as the boundaries of physical objects.

Mathematics studies these properties by abstracting them from physical objects and motion. Mathematical art, on the other hand, examines mathematical objects physically rather than mathematically. Aristotle argues that optics, which is a mathematical art, works on mathematical lines in a physical sense, not a mathematical sense. In the *Second Analytics*, Aristotle makes a hierarchical classification of science: The lower arts present empirical facts; These are the arts of optics, mechanics, music and stargazing. The higher arts are geometry, geometry of solids, arithmetic and astronomy; They explain their objects through mathematical proofs. Optics is lower than geometry, mechanics is lower

than geometry of solids, music is lower than arithmetic, stargazing is lower than astronomy. The first classifies phenomena, and the second mathematically explains "how" that phenomenon occurred. According to Aristotle's philosophy, these arts can be used to mathematically describe physical objects and processes. Every proposition in these arts is based on mathematical principles and theorems, principles of that art, and theorems previously proved in that art. Geometrical lines used in optics may facilitate calculations by representing light rays, but they are not able to answer questions such as "What is the nature of light?", "What are the causes of optical phenomena?" cannot answer physical questions like

Summary

To verify the validity of the above conclusions, the following question can be asked: What is health? Whatever the answer, what gives legitimacy to the definition of achieved health? In the Aristotelian system, health is defined as the balance of the four elements in the human body, namely heat, cold, moisture and dryness. So, did Aristotle arrive at this definition through experience? To deepen the tension, one may go beyond the Mediterranean basin and ask about the definition of health in classical Indian medicine. As you know, in classical Indian medicine, health is defined as the openness of the seven chakras.

So, did the Indian doctors arrive at the concept of health through experience? The science that gives legitimacy to these definitions is physics; that is, "why is nature the way it is and not otherwise?", which presents the common nature and common causes of individual observed phenomena as a whole. It is physics that answers the problem. Going back to Aristotle, this physical science consists of subtheories such as matter-form theory, potential-actual theory, and soul theory. These theories emphasize such doctrines as "natural earth", "closed universe", "imperishable sky", "four elements", "organic nature", and "immovable mover". In the philosophy of science, this set of doctrines, which is the basis of science, is called a paradigm. When this paradigm changes, only the practical component based on experience remains, because the physics that gives legitimacy to the theoretical parts of art also changes. A new physical science based on a new paradigm can give new reasons to the practical components of art; He can declare illegal what he cannot give. Legitimate treatments, justified by the theoretical component that Aristotelian physics provides to the art of medicine, are positioned as "alternative" treatments for modern medicine. No modern medical school conducts research on these treatments; These procedures are not used in modern hospitals. What justifies a

medical procedure, then, is not that it works, but that it is justified by an existing physical theory. An unreasoned activity, that is, an activity that is guided by knowledge of "how" without a theoretical component, is an activity that does not know why it is doing it. Since the successes he achieves are random, they are closed to development. The reason why justification by physical theory is preferred over derived benefits is that the former is open to development.

Used literature:

1. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. В DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 117–124).
2. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 108–115).
3. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. В CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 122–130).
4. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 95–104).
5. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 208–215).
6. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
7. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
8. Karimov, F. (2022). ANIQ INTEGRALNI TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 14(14).
9. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 95-104.
10. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 117-124.

11. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 108-115.
12. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 122-130.
13. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 208-215.
14. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
15. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED SYSTEM FOR CONTROLLING TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY IN PRODUCTION ROOMS. В DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
16. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. В ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 16–27).
17. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. В MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
18. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. В INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 54–63).
19. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. В МЕЖДУРОДНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИХ НАУК (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 46–55).
20. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). DATA BY COMBINING MAIL THROUGH TO SEND METHODS. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 198–207).
21. Akhmedova, Z., & Rahmatova, N. (2024). LMS (LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM) LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FEATURES. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 85–94).
22. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). IPHONE OPERATIONAL IN THE SYSTEM MOBILE APPLICATIONS TO CREATE INTENDED PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENTS. В

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 111–121).

23. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). STRUCTURES OF SMALL DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 97–107).

24. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. В DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 106–116).

25. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.

26. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.

27. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 16-27.

28. INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION

29. ОТ MURODOV - International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & ..., 2023

30. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PHYSICAL-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NA-KMS AND CARBAPOLL BASED GELS. Development and innovations in science, 2(12), 65-70.

31. Jurakulov, S. (2023, December). RESEARCH THEORIES OF PHYSICS COURSES IN JAPAN. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 43-48).16:08

